

TECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS FOR EXTENDING THE SERVICE LIFE OF HIGH-STRENGTH CONCRETE FLOORS

Volodymyr Kuchuhura

PhD Student, Kharkiv National University of Civil Engineering and Architecture

Growing demands for modern industrial and civil facilities necessitate the installation of high-strength, wear-resistant concrete floors with improved flatness and crack resistance. Currently, the issue of improving their quality and extending their service life is particularly relevant. At present, there is no modern regulatory framework for the design and installation of floors, as a result of which the selection of materials and technologies is based on the contractor's prior experience without proper engineering verification. In this case, the main criteria for choosing structures become the contractor's previous experience and the customer's financial limitations.

Analysis of existing solutions for the installation of concrete floors in industrial and civil buildings made it possible to determine that, under modern operating conditions, these floor systems have limited service lives, which restricts their reliability and functionality.

For this research topic, it is reasonable to assume the possibility of developing organizational and technological solutions for the installation of high-strength concrete floors. Such solutions would include the use of modern quality control instruments, contemporary calculation and design software packages, and specialized equipment and tools, which would make it possible to extend the service life of such structures.

Among the current key objectives are the following:

- generalization and systematization of methodological approaches, design and technological solutions for the installation of high-strength concrete floors, and development of regulatory documents for their durability;
- conducting experimental studies to determine and systematize the degree of influence of destabilizing factors that affect the durability of high-strength concrete floors;
- analyzing the static and dynamic loads of floor structures, supplemented by computational modeling, to determine their service life;
- conducting experimental testing using laboratory equipment to identify the main influencing factors and establish criteria for the durability of floor structures;
- developing organizational, technological, and technical measures that increase the efficiency of installing high-strength concrete floors and extend the service life of such structures.

***Note:** This English version is a translation of the original Ukrainian abstract published in the proceedings of the VIII International Scientific and Practical Conference “Efficient Organizational and Technological Solutions and Energy-Saving Technologies in Construction” (Kharkiv, November 19–20, 2020).*